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Imprinting system alterations indicates a conserved mechanism of resistance.

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We describe alterations in the imprinting system as a conserved mechanism of resistance in triple negative breast cancer (TNBC). Imprinting system effectors were both activated and silenced. *ZIM2* silencing was prominent and occurred concomitant with previously described Xist activation.

Citations

1. Kim, J., Bergmann, A., Lucas, S., Stone, R. and Stubbs, L., 2004. Lineage-specific imprinting and evolution of the zinc-finger gene ZIM2. *Genomics*, 84(1), pp.47-58.